

AI-powered speech: how technology helps learners speak fluently

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Abstract: This article explores how modern artificial intelligence technologies can effectively support the development of oral speech among Azerbaijani school students learning English. The topic is especially relevant, as many learners in local schools lack sufficient speaking practice and confidence. The study involved 40 students from Baku (aged between 16 and 17) and it was divided into control and experimental groups. For four weeks, the experimental group practiced English conversation with AI-based mobile applications three times a week under teacher supervision. The results showed clear progress in fluency, pronunciation, vocabulary use, and self-confidence compared to the control group. AI chatbots provided a safe and motivating environment where students could speak without fear of mistakes and receive instant feedback. The findings confirm that integrating AI technologies into school practice can make language learning more interactive, engaging, and effective, while also helping students develop communicative competence and a positive attitude toward speaking English.

Keywords: *artificial intelligence, speaking skills, language learning, AI chatbots, English, Azerbaijan*

Introduction

One of the main goals in teaching a foreign language to school students is to develop their speaking skills. These skills can later help them in adult life, for example when entering university or finding a job. Since English is one of the main means of communication around the world, knowing it is an important skill for modern youth. However, in many schools, English lessons still focus more on grammar and reading than on speaking and real communication. The same problem can be seen in Azerbaijani schools, where not every teacher pays enough attention to developing students' speaking skills or creating speaking practice during the classes.

As Isgandarova (2025) notes, the use of artificial intelligence technologies opens new possibilities for foreign language teaching in Azerbaijan and brings innovation into teaching methods (Isgandarova, 2025, p.113). Using AI and different chatbots can increase students' motivation to practice speaking. They can do it without fear of being criticized or laughed at, because interactive chatbots do not judge mistakes. Instead, they give helpful suggestions and encourage learners to continue practicing, which strengthens their speaking ability and confidence. This is especially important for school students who often feel nervous when they have to speak a foreign language. Research shows that such anxiety prevents them from expressing their thoughts freely and slows down the development of speaking skills (Ebadi et al., 2025).

In recent years, there has been a rapid increase in the number of applications and platforms using artificial intelligence designed for language learning. It is now possible to use conversational chatbots, virtual partners, and voice assistants that help learners engage in dialogue and improve their speaking skills anytime and anywhere. While some programs require special equipment such as virtual reality headsets, others do not need any additional devices. Even those who do not have computers or tablets can use these tools, as many applications are available on regular smartphones.

Communication with artificial intelligence helps students overcome the language barrier because they are not afraid of making mistakes. The program corrects them in a friendly way, suggests appropriate words, and supports learners throughout the process, making learning both interesting and motivating. According to Ashrafova (2025), the proper use of AI technologies

gives students valuable experience, helps them overcome linguistic barriers, and makes learning more engaging and accessible (Ashrafova, 2025, p. 92).

Thus, the relevance of this study lies in the need to find new ways of developing speaking skills among school students through the integration of artificial intelligence into the learning process. The purpose of this work is to find out how AI technologies help high school students develop oral speech and feel more confident when speaking English, as well as to identify the most effective ways of using AI conversational partners in classroom settings.

Literature review

Recent studies confirm that the use of artificial intelligence can noticeably improve the teaching of speaking skills. A number of researchers have focused on chatbots, i.e. programs that simulate various real-life conversations students might face. For example, in the study by Fathi et al. (2024), the authors examined how communication with the chatbot Andy affected learners' English speaking skills. During the experiment, the students in the experimental group, who practiced with the chatbot, showed better results in developing their speech compared to the group that used traditional dialogues without modern technologies (Fathi et al., 2024). In addition, students working with AI became more willing to communicate in English and demonstrated improvement in fluency, lexical richness, and pronunciation (Fathi et al., 2024, p. 80).

Other studies have also explored the influence of artificial intelligence not only on speaking skills but on reducing language anxiety as well. For instance, Ding and Yusof (2025) conducted a six-week experiment using the Mondly application. The results revealed that the experimental group achieved higher speaking performance and reported lower levels of foreign language speaking anxiety than the control group (Ding & Yusof, 2025, p. 1220).

Together, these findings suggest that integrating AI tools into language learning can enhance both the technical side of communication skills and the emotional comfort of learners. More evidence comes from the study by Shafiee Rad (2024) in the United Kingdom. The researchers looked at how using VR platforms like MondlyVR and VirtualSpeech can help English learners speak more confidently and feel less anxious. The experiment lasted six weeks. During that time, the participants worked on different communication tasks in a virtual space and, by the end, they spoke more fluently, with better pronunciation, and showed lower speaking anxiety than the control group that studied in a traditional way (Shafiee Rad, 2024, p.2). The authors mentioned that MondlyVR and VirtualSpeech created a safe, interesting atmosphere where students felt more relaxed and willing to talk.

Altogether, recent studies show that AI-based tools can really help develop speaking skills. Adding these technologies to the classroom can make lessons more dynamic and give students an opportunity to use English more freely. It can also help them overcome fear and hesitation while speaking to real people. In this article, the author describes an experiment carried out with school students in Baku to test these ideas in practice and suggest some ways to use AI tools in teaching speaking.

Methodology

Participants and Experimental Design. The experiment took place in the spring of 2025 and involved 40 high school students from Baku, aged 16 to 17. All participants were randomly divided into two equal groups of 20 - a control group and an experimental one. To make the results fair, all students had approximately the same level of English, which was Pre-Intermediate. The control group followed the regular program, doing dialogue exercises with the teacher and classmates, as well as speech and speaking tasks from the textbook, without using any modern technology. At the same time, the students in the experimental group, in addition to the main classes, were given a chance to practice speaking through modern technological tools.

Instruments. The primary tool used in the experimental group was the application Loora and a supplementary tool, ELSA Speak. Loora is an AI chatbot that has recently become one of the most popular tools for language learners (Loora AI Ltd., 2025). Many users say it

almost feels like having a private tutor, since they can practise speaking, grammar, and pronunciation whenever and wherever they want (Loora AI Ltd., 2025; Miller, 2024). Learners talk to an intelligent virtual partner that reacts naturally, which helps them feel more relaxed and less afraid of making mistakes. After a few sessions, students start speaking longer and with more confidence, trying out new words that they didn't dare to use before.

ELSA Speak, on the other hand, is a different story. It is less about conversation and more about precision, i.e. the exact sound of every word and how natural it feels in real speech. The app listens carefully, points out pronunciation problems, and gives clear feedback right away. Recent studies confirm its positive impact on pronunciation accuracy and learner satisfaction (Pham & Pham, 2025). Students often say that they enjoy seeing their progress and feel motivated when their scores improve after each session.

To make the learning process more engaging, both apps were used together (they are similar in their AI nature but different in purpose). They complemented each other surprisingly well. Loora helped students become more fluent and confident in conversation, while ELSA Speak improved pronunciation accuracy and gave them the sense of sounding more like real English speakers. Therefore, this combination created a good balance, as one tool helped students express themselves more freely, while the other helped them pay attention to form and accuracy. Together, they made the learning experience more dynamic and motivating.

Procedure. The experiment lasted four weeks. Both groups had their regular English classes during this time (3 classes a week, 45 minutes each). The classes were usually divided into three main parts.

1. Warm-up (5 minutes): students got small cards with short communicative situations in English. Many of the students were preparing for university entrance exams in geography, so the topics were often related to tourism or geography. For example: "Tell a new friend from another country about your culture's typical hobbies" or "Book a hotel room over the phone." While reading the task, they tried to remember the vocabulary they might need. If someone forgot a word or wasn't sure, they asked the teacher. Sometimes the class discussed useful phrases that could help in real conversations outside the classroom setting.

2. Dialogue with AI (30 minutes): Each student opened the Loora app on their phone and started a conversation on a given topic. Loora worked like a real speaking partner: it asked questions, answered naturally, and reacted to what students said. The topics were simple at first — things like hobbies, school life, or travel — but became a bit more complex each week. When a student made a mistake or used an awkward phrase, the app gave friendly feedback and suggested better options. It didn't interrupt or criticise, so students felt comfortable trying again. The bot corrected mistakes kindly, almost like a friendly teacher giving quiet advice. It could say something like "Try using the past tense here" or "You can say this differently." Sometimes the teacher walked around the class, helping with ideas or encouraging students to keep the talk going. This approach made students feel safe. They understood that making mistakes was normal as everyone does, even adults learning a language. After a few lessons, many learners began speaking longer sentences and sounded more confident.

3. Reflection (10 minutes): after chatting with the bot, students wrote short notes about what went well, what was hard, and which new words they learned. Then the teacher talked with them briefly. They shared thoughts, asked questions, and the teacher encouraged them to keep practicing.

4. Sometimes the experimental group also used ELSA Speak as an extra tool. After finishing their Loora practice, a few students opened the app to check how they pronounced certain words. It showed them which sounds were off and gave quick feedback. Over time, they started noticing their mistakes on their own and their pronunciation became clearer and more confident. The control group worked in a similar way, but without technology. They practiced dialogues with classmates instead of using the app. The topics were the same, so both groups had equal speaking practice. The only real difference was that the experimental group spoke with a virtual partner, while the control group spoke with each other.

Assessment. In order to see to what extent students improved their speaking, both quantitative and qualitative measures were used. The main point of comparison was the score on the final oral exam. The testing was done two times: before the experiment, as a pre-test, and after it, as a post-test.

The exam had three parts. The first was a short talk on everyday topics where students greeted the examiner and told a bit about themselves. The second was a short monologue. After two minutes of preparation, they spoke on a given topic for one or two minutes. The last task was a role-play. Students acted out simple real-life situations, for example, talking to a tourist or asking for help in a travel office.

Each performance was assessed according to four criteria: fluency, pronunciation, accuracy and coherence: fluency, pronunciation, accuracy and coherence. For every part they could get from 0 to 5 points. The total maximum score was 20 (100% = 20 points).

Students also filled out a small questionnaire about their experience during their classes. Some of the questions were like “Do you feel confident when you speak English?” or “Are you afraid of making mistakes?” The answers were given on a five-point scale from 1, meaning not at all, to 5, meaning very much. The same form was used before and after the experiment to see if the students became more confident.

Data Analysis

The quantitative data included the results of the oral exam and the numerical answers from the questionnaires. Each oral performance was scored on four criteria: fluency, pronunciation, accuracy and coherence. Every student could get up to 20 points in total, which was later converted into percentages for easier comparison. Mean values (M) and standard deviations (σ) were calculated for each group before and after training. To check if the changes were statistically significant, two t-tests were used: one compared the results within the same group, and the other compared the difference between the experimental and control groups.

The questionnaire results were analysed in a similar way to see how much students' confidence changed after training. Qualitative data, such as teacher notes and student feedback, were also considered to support the numerical results. Still, the main focus was on measurable improvement in speaking performance.

The experiment followed ethical standards. Participation was voluntary, and parental consent was obtained. Before the start, students were informed about safe internet use and reminded that AI chatbots are only learning tools, not real teachers. They were also monitored to prevent access to unrelated websites during the sessions. Overall, the aim was to keep the learning process natural while showing that AI can be safely used in real school settings.

Results

Oral Speech Performance. To understand the outcomes of the training, the data from both tests and questionnaires were analyzed. The oral exam results were converted into percentages to make it easier to compare the progress of the two groups. The mean scores before and after the training are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of Oral Speech Performance and Statistical Results

Group	Test	M (%)	σ	Improvement Δ	t	p
Experimental	Pre-test	69.5	5.2	—	—	—
	Post-test	82.1	4.6	+12.6	4.18	<0.01
Control	Pre-test	68.9	5.0	—	—	—
	Post-test	75.0	4.8	+6.1	2.10	≈0.05

As we can notice in the table, the initial results of the two groups were almost the same. After four weeks of instruction, the experimental group demonstrated a much higher progress that is about 12.6 points, while the control group improved by only 6.1 points.

At the beginning of the experiment, both groups had almost the same results, around 69–70%. By the end of training, the experimental group improved from 69.5% to 82.1%, while the control group rose from 68.9% to 75.0%. In class, students who used AI tools spoke more freely and with greater confidence. Some began using new words and expressions that they had never tried before. Several students said they felt more relaxed talking to an AI partner than to classmates. Statistical analysis using paired and independent t-tests confirmed the findings.

The improvement in the experimental group was statistically significant ($t = 4.18, p < 0.01$), whereas the progress in the control group was marginally significant ($t = 2.10, p \approx 0.05$). The difference between the two groups was also significant ($t = 2.65, p < 0.05$), indicating that AI-based speaking practice had a clear positive effect on oral performance.

Components of Speaking Skills. The biggest progress appeared in fluency and pronunciation. In the experimental group, fluency increased from 3.1 to 4.0 and pronunciation from 3.0 to 4.1 on a five-point scale. In the control group, the change was smaller: fluency rose from 3.1 to 3.5, pronunciation from 3.0 to 3.3. Students from the experimental group pronounced sounds like [θ] and [w] more accurately and spoke with better rhythm. This may be connected not only with regular practice through the app but also with their higher motivation and curiosity to try new technology. The results are illustrated in Table 2.

Table 2: Components of Speaking Skills Improvement (Mean Scores on a 5-Point Scale)

Skill	Experimental (Before → After)	Control (Before → After)
Fluency	3.1 → 4.0	3.1 → 3.5
Pronunciation	3.0 → 4.1	3.0 → 3.3
Accuracy	3.2 → 3.8	3.1 → 3.4
Coherence	3.3 → 3.9	3.2 → 3.5

Teachers' and Students' Feedback. The teacher of the experimental group noticed that by the second week, students were already looking forward to AI practice sessions and became noticeably more active in class discussions. Some of them even downloaded similar applications at home to continue training, which shows a level of self-directed learning that rarely happens in traditional lessons. A few shy students became more active after talking with the virtual partner, because they felt more relaxed.

In their written feedback, most students described the AI conversations as “fun and useful.” They appreciated that they could speak as long as they wanted and that “the AI never gets tired.” Several admitted that at first they were unsure about talking to a program, but later found it surprisingly interesting and motivating. Interestingly, some noted that AI gave them a feeling of real communication because it responded instantly in a friendly way and never criticized. A few students mentioned minor issues, such as repetitive answers or occasional difficulty in recognizing their accent; however, their overall impression of AI-based speaking practice remained quite positive.

Discussion

The results show that artificial intelligence helped students improve their oral communication skills and feel more comfortable using English. Those who practiced with the AI chat bot spoke more easily and participated more readily in discussions. The teacher noted that they were less afraid of making mistakes and often tried expressing their thoughts in different ways. For many students, the tasks felt more like interactive communication or even

a game than formal exercises, which helped reduce tension and increase interest (Kooti et al., 2025; Ashrafova, 2025).

The emotional effect was also evident. The level of speaking anxiety dropped by about 30%, which suggests a real emotional shift. Students said they worried less about being wrong, and after a few successful dialogues with the bot, they started to feel more comfortable speaking in English in general. This partly supports the conclusions of Ding and Yusof (2025), who noted that AI-based speaking platforms tend to lower speaking anxiety and create a more positive emotional background for communication.

Although the experiment lasted only four weeks, the results suggest that AI-based speaking practice can successfully complement classroom teaching. Such tools provide additional language exposure, improve self-expression, and help students use English more naturally.

Overall, AI doesn't replace teachers, but rather supports them. Such technologies provide students with more language practice, stress-free environment, boosting their interest in the subject and their self-confidence. The results are consistent with global trends and confirm that AI assistants can contribute to the development of communication skills and motivation (Kooti et al., 2025; Ebadi et al., 2025).

Conclusion

The aim of the study was to find out how artificial intelligence technologies can help high school students in Baku speak English more freely and confidently. The experiment showed that conversations with an AI partner really improved students' oral speech, and they began to speak faster, more accurately, as well as with less fear of making mistakes. This kind of practice gave them more opportunities to use the language, which is not always possible during traditional classes.

The practical significance of this study is that it confirms the effectiveness of AI platforms in Azerbaijani schools. Teachers are advised to use conversational applications as a supplementary tool, as short speaking sessions or follow-up discussions tend to produce positive outcomes.

Of course, introducing AI into schools requires certain resources, such as equipment, internet access, and suitable software. However, considering the rapid development of digital infrastructure in Azerbaijan, this seems quite feasible. As local researchers (Isgandarova, 2025; Ashrafova, 2025) note, the country is already taking steps to use AI in education. Since we live in the era of artificial intelligence and modern technology, we cannot ignore their impact on our life, but we can use them in a beneficial way and without harm to our students.

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